

Arithmos Is Not Enough For Economics
Part I: The Eidos of Man in Plato's Thought

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Abstract

Economics is focused on producing the knowledge of the relationship plane that emerged in the context of human historical drift. The accepted essence for *homo economicus* is rationality. However, approaching the complex structure of human life through this assumption alone limits the perspective of economics. Because, economics was in the process of freezing, petrified the *eidos* of its approach to human beings, and even cast it into a narrow mold of human nature. Counting, measuring, proportioning, calculating and similar operations and their institutionalized forms such as statistics, econometrics have compressed the economics into a mathematical formalism in the context of the practical needs of the market economy. Plato's dualistic approach of *arithmos-eidos* could be helpful in this context. According to this, *arithmos* and *eidos* always find a place together for themselves in our concrete and complex human reality. In this dual structure approach, economics focused only on *arithmos* and neglected the search for *eidos*.

Keywords: *arithmos, eidos, homo economicus, freedom, plasticity.*

Introduction

The scope of mainstream economics is the study of the relations between man and matter. The human being alienated from nature, in the process of coming to his own consciousness, started to see nature as a substance, a resource or an opportunity; and in the context of the survival instinct, he tended to instrumentalize the nature. The law of insoluble contradiction between unlimited needs and scarce resources or *scarcity* which is included in the generally accepted definition of economics by Lionel Robbins, is a modern interpretation of the process in question. In fact, man, who first created a subsistence economy, had gained superiority over nature in time and has been chasing power and wealth in the so-called market economy. Therefore, as a social science, economics is focused on producing the knowledge of the relationship plane that emerged in the context of human historical drift. The knowledge of obtaining optimal economic power and using this power is investigated, under the scarcity law constraint. The typology of man in this research area is *homo economicus*. In line with the understanding of the human being who alienates from nature and builds a life for himself and with his own hands by instrumentalizing nature, the typology in question assumes an essence, a nature or a substance about human beings. The accepted essence for *homo economicus* is rationality.

However, the acceptance of man's rationality is not wrong, but at least an incomplete starting point. The defense of many economists against such objections generally focuses on emphasizing that this starting point is the most appropriate methodological tool. Again, it is of course impossible to oppose human rationality, and the rationality assumption can be accepted as an appropriate methodological tool. However, approaching the complex structure of human life through this assumption alone limits the perspective of economics. As a matter of fact, the science of economics, which approaches the reality from a limited perspective or through a distorted consciousness, tends to repeat itself on the one hand, and on the other hand, gives weight to formalism in order to preserve its scientific appearance. The increasing need to develop new conceptual perspectives on human beings is being tried to be met by statistical, econometric and similar quantitative methods.

In this article, this approach will be discussed based on Plato's concepts of *eidos* and *arithmos*. Plato, one of the most important philosophers of the ancient age, is perhaps one of the most basic sources to be consulted for appropriate answers to the questions that are wanted to be answered, with his important contributions to each of the concepts needed to think. After examining his thought, the argument that Plato's *eidos* on human being may be inadequate, will be discussed by approaching from a different angle, even if Plato's emphasis on human *eidos* is appropriate. In this context, the second important

perspective discussed in this article is to question which concept can be applied as an alternative *eidōs*, by referring to the concepts of important figures of the history of philosophy.

Plato's Thought

When Plato wants to think about being, he finds Parmenides' concept of *Hen* (one or unit) and accepts it basically. This starting point can be thought of as the saying *ex nihilo nihil fit* (nothing comes out of nothing). Existence exists and is *Hen*. In Parmenides' expression, being is one (*to on to hen*). Absence or nothingness does not exist and therefore there can be no information about it. From this point of view, *logos* (word, discourse, thought) can only refer to *Hen*. However, to say that everything is one or to point to *Hen* can also be understood as saying nothing else. Thus, it can be argued that a kind of limitation on human thinking was imposed by Parmenides. According to him, research on *Hen* will only lead to artificial dualisms. For example, the concept of *polla* (many) also creates problems for people. This time, it is not known how the multiplicity will be brought into unity.¹ It is important because Plato realized that knowledge cannot be acquired when it is said and the difficulty of conceptualizing this multiplicity when it is called *polla*. To put it differently, Plato tended to think about being (*On*) or truth (*aletheia*), to talk about them through *logos*. It is necessary to explain why everything appears as the way it appears. More importantly, it is necessary to explain why everything that appears looks different over time. Therefore, Plato tries to come to terms with the most basic problems such as existence and change. On the one hand, knowing why things are as they are, and on the other hand, knowing why they are not as they are, are manifestations of this fundamental problematic.

Plato tries to open up, perhaps even surpass, the concept of *Hen* should be contented with merely pointing out its existence. According to him, man exists in *doxa*. This is an illusionary universe. However, this is not due to human or society-specific misconceptions. No matter what he does, as long as man stays on this *doxa*, he will not be able to get rid of the illusionary universe he has fallen into. As in the famous cave allegory, all the knowledge of man, his experiences from what he lived through, etc. belongs to this *doxa*. Only as a result of getting rid of this *doxa* plane, and encountering the truth man could get rid of the illusion. When Plato's *aletheia*, in other words the truth, is reached, everything can be understood in all its aspects. Existence, change and all other questions will find their answers on this plane.

According to Plato, the secret of everything will be attained through a spiritual journey that man (or rather *anthropos psukhe*) will experience enlightenment, encountering *aletheia*.² All the questions that arise in the context of human life will be answered and the meaning of human life will be determined. According to Plato, the actor of this ancient quest is a philosopher. With the help of a sage (*sophos*) who contemplated *aletheia*, the *philosophos*, the person who has the love of wisdom, will reach the truth. All kinds of questions such as why he was born, why there is death, why there is pain, why he desires, why he is full of hope and why he fears will be left behind. The person who never changes, who always stays the same, and on the other hand who changes constantly, who is not the same in any way, seeks to eliminate his ignorance. This person, who is in a lack of knowing, has been influenced by *Eros* and has been caught in a *mania* (attraction) in a positive sense. This man, this madman, or *philosophos*, wants

¹ Methodologically, it is necessary to fill the problem between one and many with distinctions, definitions and similar taxonomies. In this context, Charles H. Kahn brings the following lines to our attention: "If now we proceed methodically, we will fill the logical space between an unanalyzed unity and an unlimited plurality with a definite number (arithmos) of subdivisions, the units or ones. (These will turn out to be specific forms or kinds.) Only after these intermediate divisions have been marked is it appropriate to describe the total multitude of (sensible) instances or exemplifications as unlimited, by applying the idea tou apeirou, the concept of the unlimited many." (Kahn, 2013: 152)

² In his work titled *The Republic*, Plato describes this experience of man as a *techne* as follows: "But our present discussion, on the other hand, shows that the power to learn is present in everyone's soul and that the instrument with which each learns is like an eye that cannot be turned around from darkness to light without turning the whole body. This instrument cannot be turned around from that which is coming into being without turning the whole soul until it is able to study that which is and the brightest thing that is, namely, the one we call the good. Isn't that right?" (Plato, 1997: 1136 (§518c))

to contemplate existence, to reach the truth, to be free, to transcend the world of necessity, and of course he desires the immortality. *Philosophia* then, is a logocentric experience of *techne*, lived through the *anthropos psukhe*, who has forgotten his own truth, and which takes place on the border of *aletheia* and *doxa*. Then, to open this context, we can say that this *tekhne* is the process of creating one's own life, one's own freedom³, with one's own hands.

This experience is essentially an experience of *anamnesis*, of remembering. Man has already encountered *aletheia*, but has forgotten it. He fell from heaven to earth or lost the peaceful life in his mother's womb that he had experienced for a while. To put it differently, instead of heaven or mother's womb, it can be said that man has built a second life on top of his living life in complete harmony with nature.⁴ Full harmony with nature is essentially a pure survival life. With survival instinct the biological life that finds direction. It is a life that is essentially no different from the life of a cell, a plant or an animal. In the context of such a life, however, a person is not independent, heteronomous or free, even if he is at peace. However, what makes a person different is his *alienation* from this life style or the fact that he builds a second life as if adding a layer on top of it, without eliminating that life. This is the distinguishing quality of man. Accepting man as an intelligent creature (*animal rationale*) or seeing man as the most valuable of all living things is essentially an interpretation of this process. What makes everything we do and know possible is that this step has already been taken.

If we go back to Plato, it should be emphasized that one of the elements that makes him different is that he tries to explain the existing as well as this human experience. It is necessary to know the plane of change and continuity, or the plane on which human beings are, through *logos*. This plane, called *doxa*, is called *me on* in the ontological context in question. *Me on* is not *ouk on* (non-existent), that is, it does not exist; there is, but being (*aletheia*, *On*) is not.⁵ Therefore, *me on* is non-being and man is on the plane of *me on*. According to Plato, it is being (*On*) that will enable us to identify the non-being. Here is the entity called *On* which everything is based. It is *On* substances and needs nothing else to exist. On the other hand, *On* is what it is, it is not subject to change, it does not disappear, it does not deteriorate, it is not a subject of *phthora* (annihilation, collapse). *On* is the one that is *epekeina tes ousias*.⁶ When the

³ It is obvious that freedom has different meanings; It is generally used to mean getting rid of something. According to Doğan Özlem, this understanding of freedom points to a metaphysical/ontological meaning: "Freedom is a state of being unconditioned and unconditioned by something or an effect other than itself. ...If there is complete necessity in the universe, there is no freedom. If there is no full or complete necessity, that means there is room for freedom." (Özlem, 2016: 136) It should be emphasized that Plato mostly attributed the meaning of liberation (especially from *doxa*) to the concept of freedom. However, in this article, the concept of freedom will be used in the sense of the process of creating or constructing unless otherwise stated. It is possible to come across an approach similar to this in Erich Fromm, who points out the radical difference between being and having (ownership), within the scope of human life: "Freedom that is not arbitrariness but the possibility to be oneself, not as a bundle of greedy desires, but as a delicately balanced structure that at any moment is confronted with the alternative of growth or decay, life or death." (Fromm, 1976: 157)

⁴ In his work titled *The Open*, Giorgio Agamben uses a unique concept while trying to illuminate the dualism in question; it points to an openness that separates man from other species and from the metaphysical. (Agamben, 2004: 33-38) A separation that emerges in the process of human formation, cuts him off from his own existence and his direct relationship with his environment. Here, the potential of establishing a world of his own emerges for man and he takes action in this direction. Man is no longer just a human being as a species, he has more than a physical life. It will not be enough to comprehend it as a whole or a body formed by its organs. The openness in question is related to the production of societies, relationships or institutions by the person who pursues the ideal of happiness for himself or the openness is filled by these.

⁵ Plato explains the following in the words of the *Visitor* in his *Sophist* dialogue: "So it has to be possible for that which is not to be, in the case of change and also as applied to all the kinds. That's because as applied to all of them the nature of the different makes each of them not be, by making it different from that which is. And we're going to be right if we say that all of them are not in this same way. And on the other hand we're also going to be right if we call them beings, because they have a share in that which is." (Plato, 1997: 280 (§256d-e))

⁶ *Epekeina tes ousias* means beyond beings and/or substances. This place is called *topos hyperurianos*, and there truth can be contemplated. According to Plato's *Phaedrus*: "The place beyond heaven—none of our earthly poets has ever sung or ever will sing its praises enough! Still, this is the way it is—risky as it may be, you see, I must attempt to speak the truth, especially since the truth is my subject. What is in this place is without color and without

being is directly contemplated, it is grasped that it is *agathon* (good) or the highest. A person who is first afraid, fascinated and amazed by this majesty will then want to make it the subject of his knowledge.

The human being alienated by *Phusis* (nature) is on the way to make it the subject of his thought. In this framework, the first philosophers who thought about nature pursued an *arkhe*. The question to be answered is how *khaos* became a *cosmos*. To put it differently, the idea that there is an order, a meaning and/or a purpose in the background of everything has been reached step by step through human thought. The search for a principle or origin that provides this order should be concluded as a priority, and a solid ground for thought should be established. This origin must be the source of everything. In this context, the origin (Being or *On*) in question must be immune from any change, but it must also be capable of any change. *Arkhe* is an inevitable postulate, as already emphasized, one can get nowhere from nothing.

The being called *On* has a substance: *ousia*. *Ousia* is the essence that makes being. *On*, then, is both substance and essence. Through the *Logos*, man tries to reveal the nature of existence. According to Plato, it is possible to express this search of thought as remembering the truth (*aletheia*) or contemplating the truth (*theoria* - theory, observation). In this process, *dianoia* and *noesis* activities are carried out within the scope of *logos*. With *Dianoia*, people reason, make comparisons, reach inferences and decide. *Noesis*, on the other hand, realizes, comprehends, recognizes how it is. If the human being, who has forgotten the truth in *doxa*, wants to be able to re-connect with the truth, he must first leave behind the use of *doxa* as a basis, and must surpass (*aneteron ekbainein*) casual beings (*eidolon* - appearances of being) and perceptions (*aisthesis* - perception, *aisteton* - perceived), reject them and turn to the *eidos* as manifestations of the *ousia* of Being. Only through this experience man could be purified or experience *catharsis*. Thus, *anthropos psukhe* becomes metamorphosed and liberated.

However, the aforementioned *ousia* is also the source of various problematics that arise in the level of human being. Because *ousia* is the reason why things stay the same on the one hand and differ on the other. As much as the one that remains the same, namely the *tauton*, is also encountered with the different, that is, the *thateron*.⁷ It can even be expressed as follows: without the *tauton*, *thateron* is not possible. The problematic of change and the problem of *genesis* that emerges from there are discussed in this context. How can something be both the same and different? To give an example, how the sapling became a tree. Why does one associate the sapling with the tree on the one hand, but on the other hand, knows that the two are not the same thing. The bigger problem is essentially how life arose and why natural death came into existence.

In this context, we come across Plato's dialectical thought (*dialektike methodos*). Everything has its opposite. Thus, everything contains the potential for change within itself. It should be emphasized that Plato was influenced by Heraclitus and his idea of becoming (*genesis*), and he tried to deal with this approach in the context of *logos*. It is impossible to make a choice between Parmenides' concept of *Hen*, which blocks all kinds of *logos*, and Heraclitus's idea of *genesis*. Both close the doors to any *logos* attempt. However, Plato was in search of existence, change and their knowledge.

In other words, *Plato* is trying to open the determination of *omnia mutantur nihil interit* (everything changes, nothing disappears) with *logos* or is trying to articulate. In this direction, the *diaeresis* (identification, distinction) method is generally used. Man does not intend to give up the awareness (consciousness) he has gained. As he builds an autonomous life and develops a consciousness or awareness of his surroundings, he wants to continue his searches uninterruptedly.

Therefore, in the context of Plato's *genesis* phenomenon, the distinction between *tauton* and *thateron*, in other words, the same and non-identical (different or other) tends towards explanation. An expansion used in this context is the distinction between *peras* and *aperion*. In other words, Plato tries to understand the sameness and difference of things through the dualism of limit and limitlessness. On the other hand,

shape and without solidity, a being that really is what it is, the subject of all true knowledge, visible only to intelligence, the soul's steersman." (Plato, 1997: 525 (§247c))

⁷ Through the concept of *thateron* (different or other), Plato tried to overcome an ancient problematic.

another distinction he uses is that of *stasis* (stability) and *kinesis* (movement). Stability and movement are again concepts that help to problematize change. However, Plato's more striking approach focuses on how man distinguishes things from one another on the plane in which he lives. In this framework, *ousia*, in other words the essence of *On*, appears in everything. Plato calls this emergence *eidos*.⁸ Therefore, *eidos* is the content of the emergence of the essence of existence. *Eidos*, which is generally expressed as taking a share from *Being*, is also commonly used in the sense of form. *Eidos* is a form, of course, but not just a physical form or *morphe* in Aristotle's sense. As a matter of fact, Plato points to *genos* as another important concept. That is, things can only be understood in terms of different species, even if they have a share of the essence of the same being. Based on these distinctions of *eidos* and *genos*, man gave names to things or gave them *onoma*.

At this point, it would be appropriate to point out his differentiation from another important source of influence on Plato's thought, Pythagoras. According to Pythagoras, the universe or nature can be understood through the concept of number. In other words, Pythagoras also accepts the number as the principle of existence, similar to the search for *arkhe* of the first philosophers. The concept that Plato uses while carrying this perspective to his own level of thought is the concept of *arithmos*. *Arithmos* is the abstract tool used in the transition from one (unit) to multiplicity. Therefore, *arithmos* is one of Plato's mathematical objects, and these objects can take place in different planes of thought:

“According to Plato, the world of mathematical reasoning is the world that includes both mathematical objects and uses the method of deriving consistent results from assumptions, which is the basic method of mathematics, and where it is possible to use this method correctly. The world of pure reason, pure thought or mental intuition, as we know, does not rise to conclusions from assumptions, but to the principle that does not contain any assumptions, and turns back from this principle to prove these assumptions, and uses the dialectical method that provides them with the self-evidence and absolute reliability of this method. It is the world that can be used properly.” (Arslan, 2016: 266-267)⁹

⁸ In *The Republic*, the human mind's determination of the existence of knowables (ontology) and its desire to know them (epistemology) have an existential quality: “Therefore, you should also say that not only do the objects of knowledge owe their being known to the good, but their being is also due to it, although the good is not being, but superior to it in rank and power” (Plato, 1997: 1130 (§509b)) And in *Cratylus*, more importantly, to know is to know what reveals itself in the aspect of *eidos*: “But if neither is right, if it isn't the case that everything always has every attribute simultaneously or that each thing has a being or essence privately for each person, then it is clear that things have some fixed being or essence of their own. They are not in relation to us and are not made to fluctuate by how they appear to us. They are by themselves, in relation to their own being or essence, which is theirs by nature.” (Plato, 1997: 104 (§386d-e))

⁹ “This more constructive approach to the philosophy of nature is accompanied by a basic change in the conception of mathematics. Whereas in *The Republic* the study of mathematics was designed to turn the soul upwards, to liberate it from the darkness of Becoming and direct it toward the intelligible realm of Forms, in later dialogues the aim of mathematics is rather directed downwards, to identify structure in the realm of nature and change.” (Kahn, 2013: 158-159) The direction here is towards Being. To give an example in this context, *agathon* (good) enables us to attribute a meaning to the use of mathematics: “The Good is thus the source both of the special clarity of mathematics (its being knowable) and of the choice- worthiness of knowing it. In this way, it establishes the normative kinship between mathematics and dialectic mentioned earlier.” (German, 2019: 164; also cf. Kouremenos, 2018: 63-67) The resulting good in choosing to know *arithmos* also means that *arithmos* is good. *Arithmos* is good because it provides the ground for translating the *psukhe*, going beyond the world of the senses, and heading towards the *sophrosune*. Also, *arithmos* is good because it makes the above-mentioned *tekhne* possible through the qualities of stability and certainty (*akribeia*) in its possibility. (Roochnik, 1994: 561-562) In the light of all these details, it should be emphasized that for Plato the non-mathematical use of *arithmos* is more fundamental and only those who adopt the dialectical method (*dialektike methodos*) can act from a real solid ground that can reach the *eidos* of numbers. (Klein, 1968: 92) Unlike methods that accept their hypotheses as immutable truths, the dialectical method uses their hypotheses as stepping stones to ascend to the principle of all things. (Heath, 1921: 290) In *The Republic* the thought is expressed in the following lines: “And although those who study the objects of these sciences are forced to do so by means of thought rather than sense perception, still, because they do not go back to a genuine first principle, but proceed from hypotheses, you don't think that they understand them, even though, given such a principle, they are intelligible. And you seem to me to call the state of the geometers thought but not understanding, thought being intermediate between opinion and understanding.” (Plato, 1997: 1132 (§511c-d))

While Plato uses the concept of *arithmos*, he is aware that it has counterparts both in the *aletheia* plane and in the *doxa* plane. The *arithmos* on the *doxa* plane is rather used as a means of counting, calculating or measuring things. The *arithmos* on the *aletheia* plane is called *eidetiko arithmos*. These are rational numbers used in the search of the independent of time and space, as the manifestation of truth. Seeing the issue in question regarding the number on the plane of the unchanging:

“The concept of number should be considered together with immutability. Because each of the numbers exists in the mind separately and absolutely from the other. For numbers to be added or subtracted, they must all be based on unity that remains absolutely the same. The root of all numbers is the number One. Because of this characteristic, it must be added to, subtracted from, and infinitely divisible. How do we find this absolute immutable and identical nature? The fact that number is an ontologically ideal being, a formally tautological truth, and an epistemologically abstract concept helps to understand how it came to be. Number arises from the mind’s ability to repetition in its objectifying power. What is repeated becomes unsubstantiated and identical objects, independent of their empirical character. This is now a contentless and empty object, empty shape, or ideal object, independent of the content object that experience grasps.” (Ülken, 2014: 559)¹⁰

In *Philebus* Plato remarks that working on them, on the other hand, is essentially an orientation towards *Being*, independent of any pursuit of practical utility:

“So at the same time they have made us realize that every investigation should search for the one and many. For when you have mastered these things in this way, then you have acquired expertise there, and when you have grasped the unity of any of the other things there are, you have become wise about that. The boundless multitude, however, in any and every kind of subject leaves you in boundless ignorance, and makes you count for nothing and amount to nothing, since you have never worked out the amount and number of anything at all.” (Plato, 1997: 405-406 (§17d-e))

As a matter of fact, attention is drawn to this context in the introduction to Plato’s *Akademia: medeis ageometertos eisito mou ten stegen*. So it should be emphasized again that *arithmos* is not alone in this plane either; It plays a role together with *eidos* in revealing what is hidden in the order in the universe (*dieschematisato eidesi te kai arithmois* [he gave shapes with ideas and numbers]).¹¹ For example, if

¹⁰ However, this rationalist tradition, which created an unwavering trust in mathematics, was subjected to radical criticism both in the 19th and 20th centuries. In this context, one of the important breaks is Kurt Gödel’s incompleteness theorems: “According to the first of these theorems, a system accepted as consistent (for example, mathematics) contains at least one proposition that can neither be proven true nor false. The second theorem is that its own rules are not enough to show that a system is consistent, an external reference point is absolutely necessary. However, the first mentioned problem also applies to the wider system that includes this point. In this case, it cannot be said that a mathematical proof gives an “eternally correct” result. Therefore, other structures that can be expressed in mathematics (e.g. physics, economics) face the same problem.” (Ersel, 2016: 13) Thus, in front of a mathematical axiom (or econometric model), even if it is proven on the mathematical plane, it is necessary to consider that his miracle may be self-evident (or the possibility of being tautological), instead of accepting it as true, definite, absolute and complete without question.

¹¹ In *Timaeus* Plato’s cosmogony finds its expression in the following lines: "That is how at that time the four kinds were being shaken by the receiver, which was itself agitating like a shaking machine, separating the kinds most unlike each other furthest apart and pushing those most like each other closest together into the same region. This, of course, explains how these different kinds came to occupy different regions of space, even before the universe was set in order and constituted from them at its coming to be. Indeed, it is a fact that before this took place the four kinds all lacked proportion and measure, and at the time the ordering of the universe was undertaken, fire, water, earth and air initially possessed certain traces of what they are now. They were indeed in the condition one would expect thoroughly god-forsaken things to be in. So, finding them in this natural condition, the first thing the god then did was to give them their distinctive shapes, using forms and numbers.” (Plato, 1997: 1255-1256 (§53)) In this context, Kahn reveals an important point about Plato with his view: “This intriguing reference to normative mathematics and its connection with coming-to-be (and hence with the natural world) is left without further explanation in the Statesman. For more information on this new conception of mathematics we turn to the *Philebus* and *Timaeus*. In this connection it is noteworthy that measure and harmony both top the list of ingredients of the Good at the end of the *Philebus*. Numerical ratios play a central role in the order of nature according to both dialogues. Thus, the normative mathematics described in the Statesman as basis for the arts and crafts will reappear

only *On* were to be talked about and only *On* to be known, the concept of one (unit) would be sufficient. However, when we look at the universe, nature or the plane in which human beings are, it will not be enough when we want to know the harmony and order we encounter. Because, *On* is unique, but things can appear in large numbers. To put it in today's terms, we are faced with things that do not differ in quality but differ in quantity. On the other hand, it should be emphasized that *arithmos* is not the quality of things, but there is an order and harmony in the relations between things, which can only be understood through *arithmos*. For example, *arithmos* is not among the things that make a tree a tree. But the tree has a position in the relationships that emerge in the context of the *phusis*, and *arithmos* is a tool that can be used to detect them.

On the other hand, it should be kept in mind that within the scope of our ontological and epistemological efforts on beings, *dianoia* activities through *arithmos* will not allow man to reach a noetic way out.¹² It is not the disappearance of ignorance, but the state of *amathia* (the disappearance of the possibility of *mathesis*, the inability to learn). Through *philosophia*, *anthropos* will comprehend *aletheia* through *noesis* (perception, intuition). Therefore, contemplating the truth (*On*, *Aletheia*, *Aion*, *Agathon*, *Epekeina tes ousias*) is not possible with the knowledge of *arithmos* obtained within the scope of *doxa* and *dianoia*.

So what we need to grasp, explain, name and even instrumentalize something is to know its *eidos* first. However, knowing *eidos* (*noeton* - the intelligible or knowledge of *eidos*; *horaton* - the visible or the image)¹³ is not sufficient to relate to that thing in practical life. Man measures, proportions, calculates

in the Philebus as the principle of Limit in cosmology, and in the Timaeus as the instrument by which the cosmic artisan gives structure to the world.” (Kahn, 2013: 159)

¹² It is necessary to pause here for a moment, because the various difficulties of the concepts used by Plato may prevent us from reaching appropriate interpretations. Of course, Plato does not find the *dianoia* totally meaningless. On the contrary, it is necessary to use it in the right place. In other words, it is important what information we use when reasoning. If we consider the information we have obtained through *doxa* with *dianoia*, we cannot reach a final result and we are stuck in a vicious circle. What we can achieve with this kind of *dianoia* will be *eikasia* (imagination) and *pistis* (belief). However, *dianoia* can also be used on *noeton* (*noesis*). In the context of *noesis*, which is the highest use of the mind, being is contemplated (theory). The method here is the use of *logos* (idea) over the quiddities (*eidos*) that emerge while the essence (*ousia*) of the being is manifested. Thus, Plato tried to open the door to the use of *logos*, which Parmenides had prevented. So, according to Plato, theory (*theoria*) and idea (*logos*) are made together: while the *theoria* and *eidos* are contemplated, the idea is realized by knitting these *eidos* together and *episteme* (knowledge of the truth), which is the most valuable level for human creativity is reached. What Immanuel Kant is trying to do through the transcendental schema can also be questioned in this context: the transcendental schema makes it possible to apply the former to the latter by being homogeneous to the categories, on the one hand, and to phenomena on the other. (Soysal, 2017: 103) Kant, like Plato, tried to construct a pattern between the unchanging and the changing. But on the other hand, Kant also emphasizes that Plato's effort was insufficient: “The light dove, in free flight cutting through the air the resistance of which it feels, could get the idea that it could do even better in airless space. Likewise, Plato abandoned the world of the senses because it posed so many hindrances for the understanding, and dared to go beyond it on the wings of the ideas, in the empty space of pure understanding. He did not notice that he made no headway by his efforts, for he had no resistance, no support, as it were, by which he could stiffen himself, and to which he could apply his powers in order to get his understanding off the ground.” (Kant, 1998: 129)

¹³ It is possible to discuss these concepts over the distinction of *mundus sensibilis* - *mundus intelligibilis* or the dualism of *phenomenon* - *noumenon*. It should be emphasized that Plato turned to the world of thoughts in line with the aim of understanding the sensible world. In *Symposium*, Plato tries to overcome the illusion of the sensible world with *eidos*: “First, it always is and neither comes to be nor passes away, neither waxes nor wanes. Second, it is not beautiful this way and ugly that way, nor beautiful at one time and ugly at another, nor beautiful in relation to one thing and ugly in relation to another; nor is it beautiful here but ugly there, as it would be if it were beautiful for some people and ugly for others. Nor will the beautiful appear to him in the guise of a face or hands or anything else that belongs to the body. It will not appear to him as one idea or one kind of knowledge. It is not anywhere in another thing, as in an animal, or in earth, or in heaven, or in anything else, but itself by itself with itself, it is always one in form; and all the other beautiful things share in that, in such a way that when those others come to be or pass away, this does not become the least bit smaller or greater nor suffer any change.” (Plato, 1997: 493 (§211a-b)) Therefore, Plato finds the conclusions to be reached through *dianoia* through mathematical singulars insufficient for the purpose of reaching the truth. For example, the *eidos* of X is just X, while singular Xs are both

and counts what he perceives as *eidōs*. In other words, when mankind building civilization, establishing culture as his second nature, he takes some things from nature as they are in nature. But he never leaves them as they are. It makes them functional in the context of civilized life. To give an example, we know what a tree is, we grasp its *eidōs*, but at the next stage of our cognitive activity or when we carry the tree into human life, we take the activity of measuring alongside the conceptual knowledge of the tree. Simply put, we count, measure, and ultimately turn the tree into a useful tool.¹⁴ We cannot carry what we know of *eidōs* into our lives without *arithmos*; therefore, *eidōs* and *arithmos* always find a place together for themselves in our concrete and complex human reality.

Plato problematizes both existence and change while trying to explain what is in a constant state of being or *genesis*. Why and how something exists is associated with being, *On*. This dimension is conceptualized in *logos* through *eidōs*. At this point, it should be emphasized that contrary to the widespread acceptance, Plato did not construct a world of ideas that is beyond the physical world in which things exist and is completely independent of them. Through the concept of *eidōs*, he associated entities with existence (immutable substance), and in this context, he set up an intellectual ground for things that remained the same and changed.¹⁵ Then, besides *aletheia*, the phenomenon of *genesis* can only be opened by knowing *eidōs* and *arithmos* together.¹⁶

Another concept that Plato pointed out in the context of the concepts of *genesis*, *eidōs* and *arithmos* is *khora*. *Khora* is a kind of place of all-encompassing, ever-changing, unbalanced and heterogeneous

X (*tauton*) and different from X (*thateron*). The singular and sensible Xs are never just Xs, because they contain their opposites and therefore change. Single Xs are not *eidōs* Xs, they are images or shadows. The mathematician can arrive at a conclusion through *dianoia* from singular Xs only when he assumes that he is against individual Xs that have had a share of an X *eidōs*. (Pritchard, 1995: 145) Thus, two kinds of mathematics (arithmetic) can be mentioned: the non-philosophical kind, which deals with practical knowledge of number of sensible objects, and the non-philosophical type, which deals with knowledge of number of absolute equal units, philosophical type. As discussed in the *Philebos* dialogue, dialectics through mathematics, which is philosophical, differs from natural science, which deals with what is in becoming, and tries to reach the knowledge of the unchanging in any way. (Wedberg, 1955: 111-112) From this perspective, mathematics owing great deal to Plato, is an abstract, a priori, non-space-time method that has its own reality and is open to an infinite variety of research techniques. (Brown, 2008: 12-16)

¹⁴ In the dialogue of *The Statesman*, measuring and counting activities for practical needs in the physical world are discussed: “It’s clear that we would divide the art of measurement, cutting it in two in just the way we said, positing as one part of it all those sorts of expertise that measure the number, lengths, depths, breadths and speeds of things in relation to what is opposed to them, and as the other, all those that measure in relation to what is in due measure, what is fitting, the right moment, what is as it ought to be—everything that removes itself from the extremes to the middle.” (Plato, 1997: 328 (§284e)) However, even though it is the requirements of the physical World in question, as differences arise within the multiplicity – which is inevitable according to Plato – it is necessary to connect with an *eidōs*: “But because of their not being accustomed to carrying on their investigations by dividing according to real classes, the people in question throw these things together at once, despite the degree of difference between them, thinking them alike—and then again they also do the opposite of this by dividing other things not according to parts, when the rule is that when one perceives first the community between the members of a group of many things, one should not desist until one sees in it all those differences that are located in classes, and conversely, with the various unlikenesses, when they are seen in multi- tudes, one should be incapable of pulling a face and stopping before one has penned all the related things within one likeness and actually surrounded them in some real class.” (Plato, 1997: 328 (§285a-b))

¹⁵ So, Plato’s aim is to determine or choose how well the determinations fit the truth. While it is *eidōs* that connects the determinations in *Doxa* to the truth, it is *arithmos* that determines how close or far this connection is. Therefore, *eidōs* and *arithmos* function together in the dialectical method.

¹⁶ Thinking can be done together in terms of both *eidōs* and *arithmos*, but without substituting one for the other. Oğuz Haşlakoğlu explains this phenomenon in the following lines: “It is neither fixed in identity nor repeats in difference; constantly transferring one to the other, taking a fresh breath every moment, taking a new step, rethinking” (Haşlakoğlu, 2019: 131) In that case, the entity shows itself differently: both as *tauton* and *thateron*. It is *eidōs* that brings them together. And again it is *arithmos* that measures the order among them. While *Eidos* connects beings to *On*, *arithmos* points to their order in *me on*. The concepts of identity, difference and contradiction (*enantia*) are useless when it comes to Being. Detection of *enantia* will be meaningful in the quest to get rid of the *doxa* plane and in the context of dialektike methodos.

forces. In a way that cannot be understood from the human perspective, a continuous becoming takes place in the scope of the *khora*, and in this context, differentiation and change occur. Depicted as a constantly shaking, bubbling, boiling, chaotic place, *khora* encompasses what is expressed in the context of *eidōs* and *arithmos* and provides a basis for different things to emerge each time. To put it another way, *khora* adds a material dimension to everything, while stamping them to a measurable, countable dimension. The reason for this is that in Plato's thought, material elements (*hyle*, matter, material) are embodied (they have width-length-depth) and the basis of this embodiment is shown with geometric shapes. However, *eidōs*, as the nature of the manifestation of *Being*, will determine what kind of unity each element that gains a geometric dimension will turn into. While different units (elements, things) are formed from the same measurable basis (*arithmos*), it is the participation of *eidōs* that creates these differences. This is how the continuous state of becoming or *genesis* that we encounter in the *cosmos*, in the universe with a certain order and harmony, is understood in this way in Plato.¹⁷ Perhaps *khora* can be seen as the forerunner of the concept of space.

So, when both *eidōs* and *arithmos* are independent of space or on the plane of existence, they embody, gain width-length-depth or become spatial after the stamp (seal) of *khora*. On the other hand, the fact that beings in the physical universe are temporal must also be taken into account. Plato uses the concept of *Aion* (infinity, infinite being) in this context. The universe as a whole, *phusis*, or whatever we perceive is essentially temporal. What creates the time in question is the manifestation of the infinite being or *Aion* in a movement that progresses according to the numbers. Man perceives the being that manifests itself in time as *chronos*. On the other hand, it is an emergence that conforms to becoming (*prepon*), necessary (*deon*) and at the appropriate time (*kairon*). So it can be said that even when we perceive it as just flowing, it will be *kairon* when taken together with *eidōs* and *arithmos*. Therefore, according to Plato, we can explain time and space, as things in themselves, with *eidōs* and *arithmos*, which enable us to open anything with *logos* and think about them. While giving weight to one of these two, moving the other to the second plan may be adopted as a temporary method or as a focus. However, once this dualistic structure is decomposed, it will create problems if one dimension is adopted with methodological concerns and the other is shelved.

Economics has been oriented towards the quest to establish an *eidōs* for man. The *eidōs* of the *homo economicus* typology is rationality. In other words, rationality, which is the distinguishing feature of *animal rationale*, which has been discussed since antiquity, has been assumed as *eidōs*. What has been done after this point is to accept this *eidōs* as an essence independent of time and space, and therefore unchanging. This is not a surprising choice for the person seeking peace, order and meaning. However, experiencing astonishment and uneasiness at the constant occurrence and seeking explanations is something different; dogmatizing an explanation or meaning is another. The typology of economics on human beings is exactly in this position. In this respect, it is not surprising that the concept of *ratio*, which is one of the first searches for conceptualization of human beings and which is in the context of the above-mentioned *animal rationale*, is pursued.¹⁸

¹⁷ The meaning of the *cosmos* can be handled primarily through the concepts of order and design. However, this order (*taxis*) should not be thought of as a phenomenon that exists only in nature and/or the universe (an organic universe has a soul in ancient thought (*empsychon*)). Order is presumed both in man and in society. The harmony of the body and the soul in man, the establishment of laws in society, the determination of the status of gods and people in theology are pointed out. In this framework, it would be appropriate to understand the *cosmos* as an order in which the parts in a whole will work in harmony with each other. (Guthrie, 1975: 299-300)

¹⁸ Throughout history, human thought has been moving on the axis of abstraction - concretization. Even though it has been possible to reach a more abstract level of thought, it is also falling into the impasse of perceiving these abstractions as concrete facts. In this context, human thought moves on the line of tension between the directions that Plato and Aristotle point to, as depicted in Raphael's School of Athens fresco. The following lines of Hegel indicate the critical importance of this axis: "Corresponding to this requirement is a laborious and almost petulant zeal to save mankind from its absorption in the sensuous, the vulgar, and the singular. It wishes to direct people's eyes to the stars, as if they had totally forgotten the divine and, as if they were like worms, each and all on the verge of finding satisfaction in mere dirt and water. There was a time when people had a heaven adorned with a comprehensive wealth of thoughts and images. The meaning of all existence lay in the thread of light by which it was bound to heaven and instead of lingering in this present, people's view followed that thread upwards towards

However, in the historical drift, the science of economics froze, petrified the *eidos* of its approach to human beings, and even cast it into a narrow mold of human nature.¹⁹ Counting, measuring, proportioning, calculating and similar operations and their institutionalized forms such as statistics, econometrics have compressed the science of economics into a mathematical formalism in the context of the practical needs of the market economy.

On the other hand, when focusing on the historical process, it will be seen that in the world of subsistence economy, people have formed associations (communities and/or states), and in this context, they have turned to solidarity as their lives' *eidos* and built their autonomy through this method. It is acceptable to assume that in the process of marketization, penetrating to the human life, which emerged in a later historical period, man will be in progress thanks to the *eidos* of rationality. However, it would be misleading to think that the change in human life can only happen in this historical context, to accept that the end of history has been reached, reminding of Hegel, and therefore to assume that we can only understand man in terms of his rationality. Man, in the past, present, and future, unites, exchanges, cooperates, measures, calculates, but his distinctive feature (*eidos*) which encompasses all of these behaviors (which lies above them, transcends them by including them in the Hegelian sense [*Aufhebung*]) within the scope of freedom.

It would be appropriate to emphasize once again: economics, which wasted its energy in pursuit of *arithmos*, has put thinking, questioning or conceptualizing *eidos* in the background. Yet again in ancient times, man was conceptualized as a *zoon politikon*, in other words, as a social creature. This means that human is an entity that can only be conceptualized in the context of time-space and within the framework of constant change.²⁰ In that case, his *eidos* can also change depending on time and space. And economics has to face this change if it wants to understand the complex human reality.

the divine essence; their view directed itself, if one may put it this way, to an other-worldly present. It was only under duress that spirit's eyes had to be turned back to what is earthly and to be kept fixed there, and a long time was needed to introduce clarity into the dullness and confusion lying in the meaning of things in this world, a kind of clarity which only heavenly things used to have; a long time was needed both to draw attention to the present as such, an attention that was called experience, and to make it interesting and to make it matter. – Now it seems that there is the need for the opposite, that our sense of things is so deeply rooted in the earthly that an equal power is required to elevate it above all that. Spirit has shown itself to be so impoverished that it seems to yearn for its refreshment only in the meager feeling of divinity, very much like the wanderer in the desert who longs for a simple drink of water. That it now takes so little to satisfy spirit's needs is the full measure of the magnitude of its loss." (Hegel, 2018: 7-8)

¹⁹ The development of the typology of the human being in question can be viewed from the perspective of John Stuart Mill and his approach to the definition of the economic man: "Mill's definition of economic man has features that need underlining. Mill does not say that we should take the whole man as he is, staking our claim on correctly predicting how he will actually behave in economic affairs. This is a theory of "real man" that Senior held to throughout his life despite Mill's essay and that is also the standpoint that was later adopted by Alfred Marshall and, one dares say, all modern economists. What Mill says is that we shall abstract certain economic motives, namely, those of maximizing wealth subject to the constraints of a subsistence income and the desire for leisure, while allowing for the presence of noneconomic motives (such as habit and custom) even in those spheres of life that fall within the ordinary purview of economics. In short, he operates with a Theory of "fictional man"." (Blaug, 1992: 56) The aforementioned superficial-formalist perspective of established economics can only describe the concepts of freedom and rationality as individual level. However, according to Amartya Sen, for example, an institutional understanding can be adopted that will make it possible to ground these concepts in a very different way: "The alternative to an exclusive reliance on individual responsibility is not, as is sometimes assumed, the so-called nanny state. There is a difference between "nannying" an individual's choices and creating more opportunity for choice and for substantive decisions for individuals who can then act responsibly on that basis. The social commitment to individual freedom need not, of course, operate only through the state, but must also involve other institutions: political and social organizations, community-based arrangements, nongovernmental agencies of various kinds, the media and other means of public understanding and communication, and the institutions that allow the functioning of markets and contractual relations. The arbitrarily narrow view of individual responsibility-with the individual standing on an imaginary island unhelped and unhindered by." (Sen, 1999: 284)

²⁰ One of the approaches put forward in this direction appears in the concept of social construction of reality: "The most general answer to this question is that social order is a human product, or, more precisely, an ongoing human

Moreover, it can be argued, based on Plato's method, that the *dianoia* activity to be carried out with the scrap information of *doxa* and in the context of *arithmos* will not offer the opportunity to reach *episteme* or *agathon* (good), which is a final goal for human beings. In this context instead of man's dream of the good life or *eudomonia* (happiness), only a life of material wealth, which can only be called a life of pleasure, can be attained. In the context of such a life, the role of economics, which has accepted to legitimize itself by emphasizing instrumental reason, will be to consent to its position as a tool (*dispositif* as conceptualized by Foucault) of searches for power and wealth.²¹ From this point on, the *eidos* of man according to Plato and the possibility of a different *eidos* starting from the concepts of different thinkers can be discussed.

The Eidos of Man in Plato's Thought

Plato turned to thinking in order to make sense of the complex and incomprehensible mystery of life. It was the most fundamental problematic change. How the changing and remaining the same coexist. How could one even talk about both the changing and the unchanging? According to Plato, in order to answer these and similar questions, it was necessary to reach existence, the truth. If we could contemplate the truth, if we could gain knowledge of it, then life would be revealed to us in all its clearness.

From the knowledge of the highest truth, downward reflection was taking place. In that case, it should have been expected that the characteristics of the truth would also reflect on the lower human being. If being or truth was good, man would be good too. But man could not be as good as the being, which is an infinite and perfect whole, but he could have his share of the good. When contemplated well, it was noticed that it could be tried to be expressed with some different words. Good was also beautiful, correct and proportionate. Therefore, according to Plato, there should be goodness in human beings and qualities such as beauty, proportionality and truth that appear with its opening.

In this context, Plato tends to think about human qualities. According to him, man or *anthropos psukhe* has abilities (faculties, powers). These are *epithumios* (power of desire), *thumos* (power of anger), and *logistikon* (power of reason). Through these forces, different contingencies about human life emerge. Evaluating the origins that shape human behavior within the framework of virtues shows that Plato did not break with the measurable (*metron*) or countable (*arithmos*) ones. Contrary to what is usually attributed, Plato did not adopt a normative attitude that is completely detached from concrete reality and has the quality of *sui generis*. First of all, it is seen that each behavior (desiring, learning and getting angry) is handled in its own context. Here, it is seen that a *dianoia* activity is carried out over the scarcity and/or abundance of the aforementioned behaviors:

“On the contrary, they above all must be our encomiasts in action, by showing themselves to be true men, with the look of truly being the fathers of true men. *Nothing too much* has long been thought

production. It is produced by man in the course of his ongoing externalization. Social order is not biologically given or derived from any biological data in its empirical manifestations. Social order, needless to add, is also not given in man's natural environment, though particular features of this may be factors in determining certain features of a social order (for example) its economic or technological arrangements). Social order is not part of the 'nature of things', and it cannot be derived from the 'laws of nature'. Social order exists only as a product human activity. No other ontological status may be ascribed to it without hopelessly obfuscating its empirical manifestations. Both its genesis (social order is the result of past human activity) and its existence in any instant of time (social order exists only and in so far as human activity continues to produce it) it is a human product. (Berger, Luckmann, 1966: 69-70) Also: “Man cannot exist apart from society. The two statements, that society is the product of man and that man is the product of society, are not contradictory. They rather reflect the inherently dialectic character of the societal phenomenon. Only if this character is recognized will society be understood in terms that are adequate to its empirical reality.” (Berger, 1967: 3)

²¹ The concept of instrumental reason used here was named by Max Horkheimer as subjective reason: “Having given up autonomy, reason has become an instrument. In the formalistic aspect of subjective reason, stressed by positivism, its unrelatedness to objective contents emphasized; in its instrumental aspect, stressed by pragmatism, its surrender to heteronomous contents is emphasized. Reason has become completely harnessed to the social process. Its operational value, its role in the domination of men and nature, has been made the sole criterion. Concepts have been reduced to summaries of the characteristics that several specimens have in common.” (Horkheimer, 1947: 21)

an excellent adage—because it is, in truth, excellent. For that man’s life is best arranged for whom all, or nearly all, the things that promote happiness depend on himself. Such a man does not hang from other men and necessarily rise or fall in fortune as they fare well or badly; he is the temperate, he is the brave and wise man. He above all, when wealth and children come and when they go, will pay heed to the adage: because he relies on himself, he will be seen neither to rejoice nor to grieve *too much*.” (Plato, 1997: 962-963 (§247e-248a))

Plato also speaks of a harmony and moderation between *psukhe* and *soma*:

“When within it there is a soul more powerful than the body and this soul gets excited, it churns the whole being and fills it from inside with diseases, and when it concentrates on one or another course of study or inquiry, it wears the body out. And again, when the soul engages in public or private teaching sessions or verbal battles, the disputes and contentions that then occur cause the soul to fire the body up and rock it back and forth, so inducing discharges which trick most so-called doctors into making misguided diagnoses. But when, on the other hand, a large body, too much for its soul, is joined with a puny and feeble mind, then, given that human beings have two sets of natural desires—desires of the body for food and desires of the most divine part of us for wisdom—the motions of the stronger part will predominate, and amplify their own interest. They render the functions of the soul dull, stupid and forgetful, thereby bringing on the gravest disease of all: ignorance.” (Plato, 1997: 1287 (§88))

In fact, according to Plato, the soul itself is in harmony:

“We will. Seen from here, it is more like a kind of consonance and harmony than the previous ones. ...In what way? ...Moderation is surely a kind of order, the mastery of certain kinds of pleasures and desires. People indicate as much when they use the phrase “self-control” and other similar phrases. I don’t know just what they mean by them, but they are, so to speak, like tracks or clues that moderation has left behind in language.” (Plato, 1997: 1062 (§430e))

Dikaion (truthfulness, justice) as the principle that ensures this harmony gives unity to the forces of the soul:

“And in truth justice is, it seems, something of this sort. However, it isn’t concerned with someone’s doing his own externally, but with what is inside him, with what is truly himself and his own. One who is just does not allow any part of himself to do the work of another part or allow the various classes within him to meddle with each other. He regulates well what is really his own and rules himself. He puts himself in order, is his own friend, and harmonizes the three parts of himself like three limiting notes in a musical scale—high, low, and middle. He binds together those parts and any others there may be in between, and from having been many things he becomes entirely one, moderate and harmonious.” (Plato, 1997: 1075 (§443c-d))²²

In this context, *dikaion* should be considered as the eidos of *anthropos psukhe*. Each of the three aspects of *Psukhe* can be handled through *arithmos*, in other words, the probability of scarcity and abundance that we may encounter in them can be measured. However, the counting, measuring and calculating activities performed on this scarcity or abundance will not give the harmony sought in *anthropos psukhe*, but will only serve to determine a situation in the inner structure of each aspect. In other words, the state of balance that we encounter in a faculty of the *psukhe* or the state of virtue (*arete*) that is free from excesses manifested in the form of scarcity-abundance will not mean harmony (*harmonia*) in *psukhe*

²² The wrong or injustice in question was interpreted by Haşlakoğlu in the following lines: “This paragraph shows what kind of kakia their place is, if they are not present as virtues in *pathe*, *sophron* (purity), *sophe* (wisdom) and *andreia* (courage), which are also reported as *arete*. It also shows that it will be filled with kakia (ugliness, evil). Accordingly, *akolasia* (perversion or sensuality) in the absence of *sophron* (purity), *deilia* (cowardice) in the absence of *andreia* (courage), and *amathia* (heedlessness) in the absence of *sophe* (wisdom) will replace *arete* and abolish justice (*dikaion*). Here, injustice (*adikaion*) is a name given to the situation in Plato’s thought where virtue is completely turned upside down with another counter value. Therefore, since the right combination of these three elements will only be possible with the provision of justice; justice is possible only with the relevant *arete* in terms of the unique pathos of each compartment. In this respect, the *dikaion* should not be understood as a fourth element added to these three elements, but as the common principle that ensures the unity of these three elements.” (Haşlakoğlu, 2016: 99)

alone. For example, a person who has chastity in terms of his desires and wisdom in terms of reason may be in a state of discord in terms of anger power, so he may be in cowardice rather than courage. When approached from this perspective, *dikaion* is to have virtue in terms of each *psukhe* ability or to be able to get rid of excesses in each of them. So, *anthropos psukhe*, the owner of the *dikaion*, has both purity, courage and wisdom. That is to say, *arithmos* are the elements that enable to know whether the virtue of each faculty has been reached or not, and *eidos*, by bringing them together, are the elements that enable us to see whether the *psukhe* is ready for the journey of truth.

Anthropos psukhe can begin this journey under the guidance of a sage and only through a *periakteon* (scene changing) *tekhne*. While the dynamic force of this *tekhne* is *Eros*, the result of the process will be the liberation of the *psukhe*:

“This is why *eros*, which is at the core of *philosophia* as *pathos*, appears before us with a very special meaning dimension that cannot be understood in Plato’s interpretations. This dimension is further clarified by Socrates’ words in the Phaedrus dialogue that *eros* was actually sent as a sacred gift—for a special purpose—not for the lover and lover to admire each other. *Eros* is a gift that will free the *philosophos* from his *doxa* conviction, because it is only through ‘losing oneself’ (*manike*) by falling into the *kalos* (beautiful) that opens up from the face of the *sophos*, by ‘changing the scene’ in the *tekhne* of *sophos* in a way that transcends the conditions subject to *philosophos genesis* (*periakteon*) may be elevated by being attracted to *to on* (being). Therefore, *eros* is not a cultural, romantic or literary accident of *philosophia*, as the only *pathos* that makes it possible to overcome *genesis*, which is impossible in terms of reasoning (*dianoia*) subject to *doxa*, but sine qua non, based entirely on *dunamis* (force, power). non liberation (*luesi*) constitutes its essence.” (Haşlakoğlu, 2016: 126-127)²³

So, according to Plato, the liberation of man will only be possible through contemplation of the truth. And it must be emphasized again that truth (*aletheia*) or being (*On*) is that which is not subject to change, perishable in any way. It would be appropriate to think that this can be understood in the context of the peace that people seek or the sense of satisfaction that it gives us finally to give meaning to everything. However, this way of thinking brings to mind another possibility. As can be seen throughout history, those who believe that they have reached the truth have tended to define human freedom this time and of course to limit the freedom in question. From this point of view, it can be said that even if the truth has not been contemplated, those who claim to have it will want to use the truth in line with their *doxa* ambitions (power, status, wealth, etc.). The same can be argued in the context of the *eidos* of the human being. Those who think that they have solved the mystery of humanity may also think that they have a right to shape (format) human beings through their dogmas of truth. However, questioning the *eidos* of *anthropos psukhe* can change according to time and space and examining the contingencies created by him may perhaps offer a way out in order to overcome this problematic. Of course, it is also possible to evaluate what is expressed in these lines as a futile effort in the *doxa* swamp, according to Plato.

On the other hand, thinking that *eidos* is changeable, contrary to Plato’s thought, should not be interpreted as a change of truth, but as a manifestation of itself in a different way. Therefore, such an emergence can be problematized in the context of Plato’s concepts of *tauton* and *thateron*. However, the perspective that is wanted to be put forward here is to leave Plato’s *aletheia* wherever it is and turn our face to the contingencies in which human beings live. The contingencies in question (things, facts, events that do not necessarily occur and occur depending on time and space) are the activities creating a dynamic character that are carried out by and for oneself. In the Thought of Plato this is a specific activity:

²³ In this context, the comment we encounter in the following lines is remarkable: “*Eros* leads and seduces (führt und verführt) thinking down untrodden paths, through the atopic Other. The daimonic nature of Socratic discourse derives from the negativity of atopia. Yet it does not end in aporia. Counter to tradition, Plato made Poros the father of *Eros*. Poros means “way.” Although thinking ventures onto uncharted terrain, it does not get lost there. Because of his parentage, *Eros* shows the way. Philosophy is the translation of *eros* into *logos*. Heidegger follows Plato’s theory of *eros* when he remarks that the beat of the god’s wing touches him as soon as he makes a substantial step in his thinking and ventures onto untrodden paths. *Eros* is called *philosophos*, the “friend of wisdom,” in Plato.” (Han, 2017: 52)

“How, then, are we to understand *autourgike* as (*auto*) ‘making’ oneself (*urgike*)? The answer is hidden in the word *autourgike*: What takes place in self-creation is again the agent (*auto*) in terms of *ergon* (product, work). Thus, *autourgike* as an activity of ‘creation’ (*poiesis*) is the ‘creation of himself’ (*auto-urgike*) of the agent. So, *poiesis* finds its real meaning in the mimetic creation of himself. No matter how much the work that occurs here has an internal necessity in terms of *urgos* (activity), *auto* (self, self), subject to the external conditions of its being *ergon*, it is open to all kinds of contingencies because it contains an alterity that contains the self (*auto*).” (Haşlakoğlu, 2016: 72-73)²⁴

In this context, claiming that the *eidōs* of man is changeable, departing radically from Plato’s thought, is to claim that man has the *autourgike* feature. By directing his gaze to his founding mind as a distinctive *dunamis*, a person can get rid of *doxa*, become free for himself, and set out to create new lives (*poiesis*). Of course, this process will also depend on the external conditions of the work, and only within this framework will contingencies emerge. To put it differently, man tends to acquire *epistasthai poiein* (poietic knowledge, knowledge of creativity) (human being as *anthropos zoon logon echon*), so he cannot be reduced to the world of necessity *per se*.²⁵ the emergence of an infinite number of contingencies. The method of focusing on contingencies is to try to explain things through the relationships established with man and his environment, instead of being based on transcendence as the metaphysical point of view does, or on immanence as naturalism, materialism, universalism and the like (different kinds of positivism or determinism tendencies) do. In that case, the *eidōs* of man can be sought not in *Being*, but in his existence. This existence is varying in time and space, because the human being has the quality named *autourgike*.

Conclusion

Eidōs is one of the most important concepts of Plato’s thought. It plays a critical role in the process of finding answers to all ontological and/or epistemological questions by going from the world of illusion in which a person lives to the plane of truth. However, *eidōs* can function together with *arithmos*. In other words, *arithmos* and *eidōs* should be taken together, in an effort to measure everything and also to determine its order and harmony. Therefore, the main problematic for Plato is to give a vision to our understanding, which is stuck between the changing and the unchanging. Man will be able to try to bring an understanding with *eidōs* to what he has achieved with *arithmos*, or he will be able to position everything in a meaningful vision. What made Plato one of the most important figures in the history of philosophy was the transfer of human thought to a different plane through such a step: human thought, stuck in the stages of imagination and belief, tends to the possibility of ascending to *theoria* through *logos*.

Plato also put forward an *eidōs* within the scope of the question about the human being. In line with the understanding of *anthropos psukhe*, who has the abilities of *epithumios*, *thumos* and *logistikon*, the *dikaion* stands out as an *eidōs*. We can measure the effects of each of our faculties on our behavior, whether they are more or less. However, what is more important in terms of human life, according to Plato, is to be able to determine how they all come together. Therefore, the *dikaion*, as the *eidōs* of man,

²⁴ Moreover, Plato points out the *autourgike* feature of Demiurgos in a cosmogonic context: “Autourgike, in the context of its use in the Sophist dialogue, is a creation that takes from itself, as opposed to the human one that takes the model of divine *poiesis* from outside of itself. As human *poiesis*, *eidolopoiike* is based on the *eidolon*, which in Plato’s thought ontologically has the status of *me on* (non-being).” (Haşlakoğlu, 2014: 169)

²⁵ As it is commonly understood, man is an intelligent speaking creature. This approach to man was expressed by Parmenides as *to gar afto noein estin te kai einai* (thinking and being are the same thing). Immanuel Kant also points out that man has a tendency to seek beyond the world of necessity: “Finally, who cannot see, from the thoroughgoing contingency and dependency of everything that they might think or assume according to principles of experience, the impossibility of stopping with these, and who does not feel compelled, regardless of all prohibition against losing oneself in transcendent ideas, nevertheless to look for peace and satisfaction beyond all concepts that one can justify through experience, in the concept of a being the idea of which indeed cannot in itself be understood as regards possibility – though it cannot be refuted either, because it pertains to a mere being of the understanding – an idea without which, however, reason would always have to remain unsatisfied?” (Kant, 1997: 103)

is the dimension of truth reflected in human behavior. However, the problem we encounter here is that Plato accepts that the essence in question is immutable. Overcoming this approach by including and accepting that the *eidos* of man is changeable will bring a new questioning. A common point of different interpretations of existential thought is, in this context, the ability of man to construct and/or transform himself. From this perspective, man cannot be explained performatively over a given *eidos*. It can be said that no final schema or map of man can be drawn through research on the *eidos* in question. In other words, the essence of man should not be seen as a given principle but rather as an open-ended ability.

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